

RISK MANAGEMENT IN ESG: COMPONENTS OF THE PRELIMINARY CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE ESG RISK CANVAS

Andreia Drozda Muncinelli

Master's Student, Department of Industrial Engineering
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná
muncinelli@alunos.utfpr.edu.br

Edson Pinheiro de Lima

Professor, Department of Industrial Engineering
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná
pinheiro@professores.utfpr.edu.br

Fabricio Stocker

Professor, Instituto de Desenvolvimento Educacional
Fundação Getúlio Vargas
fabricio.stocker@fgv.br

Gianfranco Muncinelli

Professor, Instituto de Desenvolvimento Educacional
Fundação Getúlio Vargas
ext.g.muncinelli@prof.fgv.edu.br

Abstract

This paper presents the ESG RISK Canvas, a preliminary conceptual model designed to structure the ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) risk management process. Given the complexity and interconnectedness of ESG issues, the model aims to support multidisciplinary teams in identifying, assessing, and responding to risks and opportunities related to corporate sustainability. The framework consists of fifteen blocks, covering topics from materiality assessment to risk response planning. Key deliverables include gap severity, effort prioritization, identification of main ESG risks, and a preliminary risk response plan with cost estimation. The model also enhances stakeholder alignment and fosters effective communication. Organizations at various maturity levels can benefit from using the tool as a diagnostic and planning resource.

Keywords: ESG, Risk Management, ESG Risk Canvas

1. Introduction

The term ESG—an acronym for “Environmental, Social, and Governance”—refers to how organizations promote sustainability, social responsibility, and governance and ethical practices within their operations. ESG topics can range from greenhouse gas emissions to workforce diversity and anti-corruption measures.

ESG issues are complex, diverse in nature, dynamic, and interconnected, making them challenging for companies to fully understand and integrate into their processes. Employing risk management as a framework enables business leaders to comprehend their ESG exposure as well as the opportunities it may present (Massey, 2023).

ESG risk management focuses on the identification, assessment, response, and monitoring of both threats and opportunities—affecting a company’s practices, business model, and strategy. Threats may range from environmental degradation and social inequality to weak governance and ethical failures, while opportunities include investments in sustainable infrastructure and innovation in products and services. The goal is to foster sustainable and responsible business practices that benefit the organization, society, and the planet (Massey, 2023).

The aim of this paper is to propose the components of the preliminary conceptual model of the ESG Risk Canvas—a tool designed to structure the reasoning behind the initial steps to be taken toward an ESG risk management project or process.

2. ESG Risk Management

2.1 Why is risk management important in ESG?

ESG is vital for business sustainability and resilience. ESG risk management must be integrated into each organization’s existing risk management framework. All companies have key stakeholders—regulators, employees, customers, suppliers, and investors—and there has been a significant shift in their ESG priorities (IBM, 2023).

Regulators and policymakers are intensifying their scrutiny of industries, focusing on how companies are transforming the management and mitigation of environmental

and social impacts, as well as developing more robust governance structures (IBM, 2023).

This shift has created a “double materiality” lens: companies are accountable both for the risks they face and for their broader impact on society and the environment. With a renewed focus on double materiality, organizations are realizing that political and regulatory changes are risks in themselves. Failure to adapt could damage their reputation, potentially causing significant harm to their brand (IBM, 2023).

Employees and customers increasingly expect companies to uphold stringent ESG standards across their supply chains. In response, many organizations have adopted impartial hiring practices and supply chain monitoring. This trend underscores that ESG compliance is important not only for regulatory reasons but also as a business necessity driven by stakeholder expectations. At the same time, companies are feeling pressure from their suppliers, who themselves must meet increasingly rigorous standards. This external pressure is prompting organizations to adopt sustainable and ethical practices throughout their value chain (Massey, 2024).

Although sometimes it is slower to take immediate action, investors are asking increasingly pointed questions about companies’ ESG practices. This heightened scrutiny is pushing many firms to reassess their ESG approach, recognizing that although investor demands are not yet fully mandatory, the tide is turning. Companies are beginning to see the need to adopt ESG strategies before stricter requirements inevitably take effect (Massey, 2024).

Organizations are generally redefining their broader purpose and focusing on becoming more sustainable. There is also a broader cultural shift in how organizations perceive their purpose. However, it is often overlooked that ESG also contributes to making companies more resilient (Massey, 2024).

As organizations set ambitious targets—such as achieving net-zero carbon emissions—ESG risk management becomes even more critical. Integrating ESG into existing risk management frameworks and business processes is becoming a core aspect of corporate strategy, driving cultural change and making ESG an essential part of how companies operate in today’s world (Massey, 2024).

2.2 How do you manage ESG?

The first step in managing ESG is to understand what the ESG risks—both threats and opportunities—are for your business. Exploring and identifying a comprehensive

ESG risk framework enables an organization to describe its business environment more accurately, providing greater depth and understanding for defining a realistic corporate purpose (Massey, 2023).

To manage ESG effectively, a comprehensive approach is also required, incorporating a robust risk appetite framework alongside the right combination of policies and procedures, technologies, and training opportunities (Massey, 2024).

2.3 Tracking and analyzing ESG metrics

From a risk management perspective, companies must first identify and assess their ESG risks. They should then adopt mitigation strategies and continuously monitor these efforts by tracking a variety of metrics, including performance indicators. From a risk standpoint, companies are revisiting and adapting their risk appetite frameworks. It is essential to consider the most appropriate metrics, targets, and tolerances to be designed.

New risks are emerging that organizations must manage, such as the potential for “greenwashing”—the practice of misleading stakeholders about a company’s ESG performance—which can cause significant reputational and brand damage (IBM, 2023).

2.4 How do you respond to ESG risk?

Responding to ESG risk requires a proactive and strategic approach, and it is essential to develop risk mitigation plans that help strengthen the control of the environment. Examples of such proactive plans may include:

- Environmental: Implementing sustainable practices such as reduction emissions, resource conservation, and investment in renewable energy.
- Social: Fostering a diverse and inclusive workplace, engaging with communities, and ensuring ethical practices in the supply chain.
- Governance: Upholding high standards of corporate governance, including transparent accounting practices and effective oversight board.

To support proactive ESG risk management planning, several risk treatment classification methods exist, each offering a different approach to determining the best way to address risk. Risk responses can be categorized into four main strategies:

- Eliminate – Completely remove the threat by changing processes, replacing materials, or discontinuing high-risk activities.
- Mitigate – Reduce the likelihood or impact of the risk through controls, training, or operational changes.
- Transfer – Shift the impact of the risk to third parties, such as insurers, outsourcing agreements, or contractual clauses.
- Accept – Either passively, when the organization accepts the risk without additional measures, or actively, when it incorporates actions to monitor and respond quickly if the risk occurs.

When evaluating risk treatment options, it is advisable to begin by:

- Identifying existing best practices for addressing the risk effectively.
- Developing risk treatment plans aimed at reducing residual risk to an acceptable level within the organization's risk appetite.
- Assessing the costs of each treatment option and weighing them against potential benefits to ensure a balanced and informed decision-making process.

It is important to emphasize the need to develop a formal strategic action plan and roadmap that integrates risk mitigation efforts, which may extend over three to five years. The plan should encompass the integration of both Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)—a structured, consistent, and continuous process for managing a company's risks—and Business as Usual (BAU) operations, prioritizing actions, assigning ownership to specific workstreams, and setting clear completion deadlines. Regular updates and reports should be provided to the organization's risk committee and board to ensure ongoing oversight and progress.

Incorporating ESG into Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) Frameworks

Figure 1 – Integrating ESG into the ERM Framework. Source: adapted from Massey, Martin (2024). How to Manage ESG Risk

2.5 In the Supply Chain

A key focus for organizations is the integration of ESG into their third-party risk procurement processes.

Companies will seek to align with suppliers who share similar corporate values regarding ESG and climate change. They may choose to work with or source from a given supplier, or alternatively, agree on an action plan to address any concerns, which can then be monitored over an agreed period.

By embedding ESG considerations into the procurement process, organizations signal to current and potential suppliers the importance they place on ESG issues, while also creating a mechanism for monitoring future carbon emissions.

This can be achieved through due diligence during supplier selection, as well as through ongoing performance monitoring and contract renewal.

It is important to emphasize that ESG supplier assessment should be based first on the design of a robust scoring system for each main risk category, and second on an overall scoring framework linked to a Red–Amber–Green (RAG) rating system to track and manage the status of risks.

3. History of Canvases

In the chapter discussing the A3 Report, Liker (2007) begins with a thought-provoking statement: “Problem solving is about thinking. But writing things down can help you think.” In other words, the process of idea development can be aided through documentation.

The A3 Report originated from the management tradition of the Toyota Model, in which the aggressive pursuit of waste elimination is one of its hallmarks. The history of this report should be told with the fewest possible words, focusing less on elegance and more on facilitating communication among those involved in solving the problem at hand. The information presented is only what is essential.

A historical detail: the information had to fit on an A3-sized sheet (297 × 420 mm) originally, as this was the maximum size supported for transmission via fax machines, the communication technology available at the time.

In any case, the emphasis was on the simplicity of use (pencil, eraser, and paper) and on providing information that could be explained in quick sessions, lasting only a few minutes, where participants could grasp the situation and make decisions from that point forward. It was a basic structure that maintained focus and direction in problem solving.

Visualization of information is critically important to provide a holistic view and enable alignment of thinking among participants. The original A3 report model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Original A3 Report Model (Liker, 2007), adapted

As an evolution of this basic problem-solving structure that maintained focus and direction, alternative approaches began to emerge with a fixed structure in the form of a preformatted visual map containing specific blocks aimed at addressing specific problems. Some concepts are characteristic of these visual models: visual thinking, systems thinking, co-creation, simplicity, and applicability.

The Canvas strategy gained popularity and has been used very productively for various activities such as innovation, lean management, coaching, marketing, startups, and change management (Scherer, 2018). According to Scherer (2018), the most commonly used models in the Brazilian context are:

- Business Model Canvas: A strategic management tool that allows for the development and sketching of new or existing business models. Created by Alexander Osterwalder, it was popularized through his book *Business Model Generation* (Osterwalder, 2009) and his doctoral thesis (Osterwalder, 2004).

- Project Model Canvas: Developed by Professor José Finocchio to help project managers prepare a Project Charter, disseminated through his book Project Model Canvas – Gerenciamento de Projetos Sem Burocracia (Project Management Without Bureaucracy) (Finocchio, 2013).

4. ESG Ontology

An ontology is a conceptual model that defines a set of categories and their interrelationships, with the aim of representing the knowledge of a given domain. In other words, it is a structured way of organizing and classifying information, establishing a common vocabulary and the connections between different elements. In contexts such as information technology, artificial intelligence, and data science, ontology is used to facilitate understanding and information exchange between systems and people, ensuring that all parties share a common understanding of the concepts involved.

For example, in an ESG risk ontology, categories such as “environmental risks,” “social risks,” and “governance risks” would be defined, specifying how these risks relate to one another and how they can be measured. However, the current need lies in reaching the stage of identifying these risks.

5. The ESG Risk Canvas

The proposed solution is a conceptual structure designed to organize a set of blocks—each corresponding to a set of information—representing an initial brainstorming exercise to structure the reasoning behind the first steps toward an ESG risk management project or process (shown in the figure 3). This structure assists in gathering data and carrying out the reasoning necessary for developing the action plan and providing a preliminary estimate of investments and expenses. It also correlates and integrates the conceptual blocks to improve the efficiency of complex tasks and ensure a real connection with the problem to be addressed.

Key objectives of the proposed ESG Risk Canvas include:

- Building a corporate knowledge base that will eventually help retrieve information and provide a space to store and share the organization’s know-how.
- Storing and sharing past findings from ESG risk management activities.

- Providing a mechanism for internal evaluation of these findings.
- Improving and encouraging communication and knowledge sharing.
- Ensuring an even distribution of tasks among the team.
- Encouraging the team to continuously improve the structure, program, and processes, in addition to daily activities.
- Stimulating the team to be innovative and to use and learn new tools and techniques.

COMPANY:

ESG RISK CANVAS

Figure 3 – ESG Risk Canvas

The ESG Risk Canvas is composed of fifteen blocks, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – ESG Risk Canvas Blocks

<p>Company Business Line</p>	<p>This field is to be completed with a description of the company’s business activities, specifically in relation to the ESG concept in its operations. It should describe how the company engages with its customers, employees, shareholders, and surrounding community, as well as its impact on business outcomes.</p>
------------------------------	---

Strategic Goals	<p>In the book “Planejando estrategicamente a empresa” (Strategic Business Planning, 2004), Carlos O. Bertero and Isabela B. Curado define strategic goals as broad, long-term objectives that guide the organization in its competitive trajectory. These goals derive from the company’s vision and mission and serve as guidelines for strategic planning. They should be clear, challenging, and measurable, while also being aligned with the organization’s internal and external environment. Defining these goals requires consideration of factors such as market positioning, available resources, and innovation capacity, ensuring coherence with corporate objectives (Bertero, 2004).</p>
Stakeholders and Shareholders	<p>In ESG, stakeholders include all parties affected by the company’s activities, such as customers, employees, suppliers, communities, governments, and shareholders. They have varied interests, including sustainability, social responsibility, and ethical governance (Freeman, 1984). Shareholders, in contrast, are a subset of stakeholders—investors who own equity in the company and focus on financial returns. In the ESG context, shareholders are also expected to consider sustainable practices to ensure long-term value (Garriga, 2004).</p>
Materiality – Environmental Axis (E) Materiality – Social Axis (S) Materiality – Governance Axis (G)	<p>The identification and prioritization of material topics—or materiality—forms the principle determining which critical issues are sufficiently important to be considered in strategic management for organizational success. Traditionally, materiality has been defined in the context of financial reporting, referring to information related to economic value creation. However, its meaning has expanded to include risks (threats and opportunities) related to sustainability issues that affect environmental, social, and governance (ESG) matters and that impact organizational performance and/or stakeholders in the short, medium, and/or long term.</p>
Risks – Environmental Axis (E) Risks – Social Axis (S) Risks – Governance Axis (G)	<p>ESG risk management focuses on identifying, assessing, responding to, and monitoring risks (threats and opportunities) affecting a company’s practices, business model, and strategy. Threats range from environmental damage and social inequality to weak governance and ethical failures. Opportunities include investment in sustainable infrastructure and innovation in</p>

	products and services. This block should identify and prioritize controls and treatments for ESG risks, including both internal and external options, exploring risk governance and how ESG can be practically embedded into strategy and risk appetite.
Risk Responses – Containment/Contingency	Compare effective treatments for ESG risks and explore the key elements of an ESG strategic plan. Understand the evidence of progress, prepare reports for management and external disclosures, and develop an ESG strategic plan tailored to your business context. Reflect on this plan and consider how others may apply it. Examine how to monitor scenario changes toward different ESG futures.
Regulatory Environment	In the ESG context, the regulatory environment refers to the set of rules, laws, and guidelines governing corporate practices in environmental, social, and governance domains. This environment is critical to ensuring that companies adopt sustainable and ethical behaviors aligned with stakeholder interests and expectations for transparency and social responsibility. ESG regulations are constantly updated to address evolving global concerns, such as environmental issues, human rights, and corporate governance practices. This includes requirements ranging from environmental and social risk disclosures to standards promoting sustainability in business. Examples include Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) – European Union (2021): Requires investors and financial institutions to disclose how ESG factors are integrated into investment decisions. Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) – European Union (2021): Requires greater transparency in ESG disclosures by companies, expanding the scope and detail of reports. Socio-environmental Responsibility Law (Brazil) – Law No. 12.305/2010: Establishes guidelines for the National Solid Waste Policy and environmental management in Brazil, promoting sustainable practices. General Data Protection Law (LGPD) – Brazil (2018): Imposes rules for the processing of personal data, a central governance aspect of ESG.
3rd Party	In the ESG context, third party refers to any external entity interacting with the organization, including suppliers, service providers, business

	partners, and investors. These parties can directly or indirectly affect the company’s environmental, social, and governance aspects. ESG third-party management involves assessing risks associated with these relationships, ensuring that they follow sustainable practices, respect human rights, comply with environmental regulations, and adopt good governance practices, thereby reducing compliance and reputational risks.
Investments and Expenses	Investment and expense figures will be derived directly from the Action Plan and must be initially estimated to support decisions on annual budget availability and the source of funds. These preliminary estimates are inherently inexact and must be refined later. The guiding rationale is that the cost–benefit relationship of the proposed actions must be considered.
Measurement and Auditing	Following the implementation of ESG actions, audits and measurements are essential to verify their effectiveness and ensure continuous improvement. Independent audits assess compliance with standards and regulations, identifying gaps and opportunities for enhancement. Measurements track key indicators such as emissions reduction, workforce diversity, and corporate governance. The use of frameworks such as GRI, SASB, and TCFD facilitates standardization and transparency of results. These processes ensure the credibility of ESG initiatives and strengthen stakeholder trust. Adopting a capital-based decision-making approach helps understand and manage interdependencies between ESG objectives, thereby enabling trade-off management and leveraging synergies (OECD, 2023).

To improve interaction within the multidisciplinary group, and to promote a didactic and incremental construction process, the ESG Risk Canvas is directly derived from the A3 Report, encompassing the following phases:

- Problem Definition and Description
- Problem Analysis
- Implementation Plan
- Results
- Future Steps

6. The ESG Risk Canvas Session

Fernando Trías de Bes, in his A–F innovation model, states that “the creator is responsible for suggesting ideas throughout the innovation process. Their ideas are intended to become innovations” (Trías de Bes, 2010). He also notes that organizations may lack creative individuals, in which case there are three possible options:

- train internal staff in creative techniques.
- recruit new people with a creative profile; or
- acquire creativity from other organizations.

The ESG Risk Canvas is, in this sense, a creativity tool.

The use of sticky notes is recommended due to their ability to adhere to a variety of surfaces and the fact that they can be attached and removed multiple times (Straker, 1997). The use of these small adhesive papers assists in the collection, organization, and subsequent utilization of information. The information is written down and placed on the ESG Risk Canvas, resulting in a set of options that can later be validated or revised.

Compared to traditional brainstorming methods, their use brings some highly positive differences due to their flexibility (Straker, 1997):

- Efficient use of time: There is no need to wait for your turn—just to write and stick.
- Effective data collection: Everyone in the session is always engaged; it is rare for someone to remain idle while others work.
- Open participation: There should be no dominance by a single individual.
- Focus on ESG Risk: The focus on the individual is reduced; the focus on the work itself is stronger.

Each field is filled in according to the suggested sequence—there is a logical order of reasoning supported by this sequence, derived from ontology and the user journey. It should be noted that the fields are intuitive and virtually self-explanatory.

One of the strategies of Design Thinking (Brown, 2010) is precisely to break down large teams into smaller, more reality-oriented groups. The idea is that this small, focused group defines the general reference framework.

Figure 4 – Step-by-step guide to completing the ESG Risk Canvas

There is a sequence of steps that should be followed in the order indicated by the arrows, as shown in Figure 4 above.

7. Conclusions

The purpose of this article was to propose a preliminary conceptual structure for an ESG risk management process. This structure, named the ESG Risk Canvas, is composed of fifteen blocks: COMPANY BUSINESS LINE, STRATEGIC GOALS, STAKEHOLDERS AND SHAREHOLDERS, MATERIALITY – ENVIRONMENTAL AXIS (E), MATERIALITY – SOCIAL AXIS (S), MATERIALITY – GOVERNANCE AXIS (G), RISKS – ENVIRONMENTAL AXIS (E), RISKS – SOCIAL AXIS (S), RISKS – GOVERNANCE AXIS (G), RISK RESPONSE – CONTAINMENT/CONTINGENCY, REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT, 3RD PARTY, MEASUREMENT/AUDITING, and INVESTMENTS AND EXPENSES.

This model proves to be an effective tool for structuring the ideas and concepts of the multidisciplinary team necessary for conceiving, planning, and executing such a project. Additionally, its use promotes effective communication within the team,

aligning stakeholder perspectives and preventing future misunderstandings and communication failures.

The main deliveries of the ESG Risk Canvas include:

- Understanding the actions required for ESG Risk compliance
- Assessing the severity of gaps
- Determining focus efforts
- Identifying key risks in the three axes (E, S, and G)
- Initiating the risk response plan
- Preparing the preliminary cost estimate for the risk response plan

One of the most significant deliverables—the risk response plan—is derived from the logical and sequential reasoning that results from completing the other fields. Each field is completed in accordance with the suggested sequence, which is supported by the ontology and the user journey.

The use of sticky notes assists in the collection, organization, and subsequent utilization of information. The information is written and affixed to the ESG Risk Canvas, resulting in a set of options that can be validated or revised.

Some companies have already been concerned with ESG for some time—regardless of the ESG Risk framework—and therefore have a higher level of maturity in their ESG risk management processes. Even for such companies, continuous improvement remains essential, and the ESG Risk Canvas can still be a valuable tool.

8. References

- BERTERO, Carlos O.; CURADO, Isabela B. *Planejando estrategicamente a empresa*. Rio de Janeiro: FGV, 2004.
- BROWN, Tim. *Design thinking: uma metodologia poderosa para decretar o fim das velhas ideias*. Rio de Janeiro : Elsevier, 2010
- ELKINGTON, John. *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*. Oxford: Capstone, 1997.
- FINOCCHIO Junior, José. *Project Model Canvas - Gerenciamento de Projetos Sem Burocracia*. São Paulo: Elsevier - Campus, 2013.
- FREEMAN, R. Edward. *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Boston: Pitman, 1984.

- GARRIGA, Elisabet; MELÉ, Domènec. Corporate Social Responsibility Theories: Mapping the Territory. *Journal of Business Ethics*, v. 53, n. 1/2, p. 51-71, 2004.
- IBM. (2023). The ESG Data Conundrum, IBM Institute for Business Value: <https://www.ibm.com/thought-leadership/institute-business-value/en-us/report/esg-data-conundrum> (accessed 13 September 2024).
- KAPLAN, Robert S.; NORTON, David P. *Strategy Maps: Converting Intangible Assets into Tangible Outcomes*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press, 2004.
- LIKER, Jeffrey K.. *O modelo Toyota: manual de aplicação*. Porto Alegre : Bookman, 2007.
- MASSEY, M. (2023). How to build climate resilience, Kogan Page, <https://www.koganpage.com/risk-compliance/how-to-build-climate-resilience> (accessed 13 September 2024).
- MASSEY, Martin (2024). How to manage ESG risk. 22 November 2024. https://advanceonline.cam.ac.uk/blog/how-to-manage-esg-risk?utm_source=SFM&utm_medium=email&utm_content=https%3A%2F%2Fadvanceonline.cam.ac.uk%2Fblog%2Fhow-to-manage-esg-risk&utm_campaign=Nurture_CAO_SA_ADHOC_ESG_Blog_5.%20How%20to%20manage%20ESG%20risk&WT.mc_id=Nurture_CAO_SA_ADHOC_ESG_Blog_5.%20How%20to%20manage%20ESG%20risk
- OECD (2023), *Managing Climate Risks and Impacts Through Due Diligence for Responsible Business Conduct: A Tool for Institutional Investors*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/8aee4fce-en>.
- OSTERWALDER, Alexander; THE BUSINESS MODEL ONTOLOGY A PROPOSITION IN A DESIGN SCIENCE APPROACH. *Diplômé postgrade en Informatique et Organisation (DPIO) de l'Ecole des HEC de l'Université de Lausanne Pour l'obtention du grade de Docteur en Informatique de Gestion*, 2004
- OSTERWALDER, Alexander; PIGNEUR, Yves. *Business Model Generation*. Alta Books, 2009.
- PORTER, Michael E. *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York: Free Press, 1985.
- SCHERER, Felipe. 15 Canvas para fazer a inovação decolar. <https://exame.abril.com.br/blog/inovacao-na-pratica/15-canvas-para-fazer-a-inovacao-decolar/>. Acesso em 16 de janeiro de 2018.

STRAKER, David. Rapid problem solving with Post-It® Notes. Da Capo Press, 1997.
TRÍAS DE BES, Fernando; KOTLER, Philip. A Bíblia da inovação. São Paulo : Leia,
2011.